

Mapping and prioritising landscape feature restoration in agricultural landscapes: A case study in Brandenburg, Germany

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ABSTRACT

EU agricultural landscapes are vital for biodiversity. Intensive agricultural practices constitute, however, key drivers of biodiversity loss. The EU Biodiversity Strategy for 2030 aims to restore “at least 10 % of agricultural area under high-diversity landscape features”, yet it lacks specific guidance for assessment and implementation. Here, we develop an approach to (a) map and assess agricultural landscape features (LF) cover at a landscape scale, (b) cluster agricultural landscapes by complexity using both compositional and configurational heterogeneity metrics, and (c) prioritise landscapes and sites for LF restoration by targeting areas of lower productivity and higher erosion risk, to enhance farmer acceptance and increase restoration benefits. Using Brandenburg, Germany, as a case study, we found that 94.4 % of landscapes fall short of the 10 % landscape features cover target. We categorised five agricultural landscape types ranging from simple to complex mosaics. At the local scale, in ten randomly selected landscapes, we identified an additional 11 % of agricultural areas on which LF could be restored. Our study helps advance methodologies to prioritise LF restoration. It can provide guidance for administrators and planners to assess the LF status and advance their adoption by farmers. We recommend prioritising landscapes and selecting restoration actions based on overall landscape complexity assessment. At the local scale, we recommend participatory processes involving local stakeholders. We believe our methodology is transferable to other EU regions, and highlights both the opportunities and challenges in developing a standardised, EU-wide approach for prioritising LF restoration to support agroecological transitions in Europe.

1. Introduction

Agricultural land use and practices are key drivers of biodiversity losses (IPBES, 2019b; Ramankutty et al., 2018), contributing to severe declines among monitored taxa such as farmland birds and insects, including pollinators (Blüthgen et al., 2023; Bowler et al., 2019; Gregory et al., 2019; Maes et al., 2020). Agriculture is also one of the main sectors driving climate change (Calvin et al., 2023). At the same time, both biodiversity loss and climate change directly impact agricultural production, for example, through the loss of pollinators or natural pest control (TEEB, 2018; IPBES, 2019a) or through climate-induced weather extremes such as droughts, fires and floods (Calvin et al., 2023).

Nevertheless, agricultural land can provide important habitats for biodiversity (IPBES, 2019a), and when managed sustainably, can contribute to mitigating climate change (Calvin et al., 2023). Key to this are agricultural landscape features (LF), defined as “small fragments of non-productive natural or semi-natural vegetation in agricultural landscapes” (Czúcz et al., 2022a). LF promote biodiversity by creating and connecting heterogeneous habitats which offer shelter, breeding and wintering sites, as well as food for a wide range of species (e.g., Batáry et al., 2010; Belfrage et al., 2015; Holland et al., 2017; Kleijn et al., 2006). They also support Nature’s Contribution to People (NCP), delivering both private goods that benefit yields, income and wellbeing of farmers as well as public goods that offer broader benefits to society as

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a whole. Examples of private goods provided by LF include pollination and pest control (e.g., Dainese et al., 2019; Holland et al., 2017; Klinnert et al., 2024) as well as mitigation of soil erosion (e.g., Holland et al., 2017). On the other hand, public goods provided by LF include improved climate mitigation and adaptation through increased carbon sequestration (e.g., De Stefano and Jacobson, 2018; Golicz et al., 2021; Muchane et al., 2020), enhanced water retention and filtration, which result in more resilient agroecosystems capable of withstanding droughts and floods (e.g., Lajos et al., 2020; Muchane et al., 2020; Wilcox et al., 2022), and cultural values such as recreational, aesthetic and spiritual values (e.g., Ridding et al., 2018). Differentiating between private and public goods is not always possible (e.g., the reduction of flood risks can benefit both private individuals and a wider public). However, this distinction may emphasise that the beneficiaries of LF often differ from its providers (Rieb and Bennett, 2020; Vermunt et al., 2020) as LF benefits are spatially and temporally heterogeneous varying across landscapes and among farms depending on factors such as land use, land use history, management practices, the ecological condition of the LF, and the perception of their value by individuals (Garau et al., 2023; Rieb and Bennett, 2020). Given the many benefits that LF provide, their installation and management should be considered as a significant agroecological practice (HLPE, 2019; Wezel et al., 2009).

Recognising the ecological and societal importance of LF, as well as their ongoing decline in European landscapes (Czúcz et al., 2022a; Haddad et al., 2015; Pe'er et al., 2022), the European Union (EU) aims to preserve, restore and improve LF infrastructure. Several initiatives within the EU's Green Deal are key to achieving this, especially the Farm to Fork Strategy, the EU Biodiversity Strategy for 2030, and the EU Green Infrastructure Strategy. Among these, the Biodiversity Strategy for 2030 sets a specific target to achieve "at least 10 % of agricultural area under high-diversity landscape features" (referred hereinafter as the *LF target*) (EU, 2020). The *LF target* is also included in the EU's Nature Restoration Regulation (NRR) as one of three agricultural indicators (EU-COM, 2024b). In the Common Agricultural Policy (CAP), as of the funding period of 2023–2027 farmers are required to maintain and protect LF through Good Agricultural and Environmental Conditions (GAEC 8), although recent political developments have introduced many exceptions (EU-COM, 2024a). To restore LF, Member States can design Agri-Environmental-Climate Measures (AECM), eco-schemes and investment measures in the CAP. These, and other payment schemes, can serve as mechanisms to reward the public goods provided by farmers through LF restoration, maintenance and protection.

Whilst LF offer many benefits, their protection and restoration into agricultural areas poses significant challenges and barriers due to high opportunity costs: Those include land ownership issues (e.g., the prevalence of tenant farming), technical challenges (e.g., required equipment), ecological concerns (e.g., LF as potential sources of pests, weeds or plant diseases), economic impacts (e.g., implementation and management costs, restriction on production and lack of financial incentives), administrative obstacles (e.g., compliance control and cumbersome documentation requirements), and social factors (e.g., negative perceptions and lack of knowledge of LF benefits), all of which contribute to both the perceived and actual costs of LF (Blanco et al., 2020; Castro Campos, 2022; Dockès et al., 2019; EU CAP Network., n.d.; Klebl et al., 2024; Massfeller et al., 2022). Understanding and addressing these barriers is crucial for increasing farmer acceptance and, thus, LF restoration for reaching the *LF target* (Goggins et al., 2023; Massfeller et al., 2022; Schroeder et al., 2015).

Yet the successful implementation of the *LF target* is also hindered by the lack of a comprehensive, standardised, EU-wide LF dataset. Although efforts are ongoing to map LF (Czúcz et al., 2022b; Rubio-Delgado et al., 2024), the available data is often incomplete and fragmented. For example, LF are recorded through the EU's Integrated Administration and Control System (IACS), a key tool for the monitoring of CAP implementation. However, it only includes farms supported by the CAP and, even then, not all LF are accounted for (Leonhardt et al.,

2023). Further, while remote sensing technologies have been used to map LF, such as the Small Woody Features (SWF) dataset from Copernicus, the resulting data frequently lacks details of small features, and is often incomplete in areas with poor satellite coverage (Golicz et al., 2021). An additional challenge is the lack of a coherent and quantifiable definition of LF, particularly "high-diversity" LF, as referenced in the *LF target* (Czúcz et al., 2022b). This lack of clarity hinders the operationalisation of the *LF target*, making it difficult to translate into clear implementation and prioritisation strategies for LF restorations across EU regions. Finally, while the *LF target* is formulated at the EU and national level, its implementation will take place at the local level (i.e., in farms and fields). This requires a downscaling approach to identify potential LF restoration sites that are feasible and acceptable for farmers to implement – potentially minimising costs while maximising benefits for both ecosystems and people.

To advance in addressing the gaps between the *LF target* and its practical implementation, this study conceptualises a methodological approach at both landscape and local levels, focusing on the following research questions:

- How to map and evaluate the current cover of LF?
- How can agricultural landscapes be categorised in terms of landscape heterogeneity for restoration prioritisation?
- How to prioritise restoration at the local scale to assist spatial targeting and landscape planning?

We test and demonstrate this methodology using Brandenburg, Germany as a case study and then discuss strategies for the prioritisation of restoration sites, considering the challenges of scaling down from the EU target, through national and subnational levels, down to landscapes and fields to support farmers, regional planners and administrators.

2. Material and methods

2.1. Study area

Our case study is Brandenburg, a federal state in Germany, which covers 29,654 km², 45 % of which is agricultural land (Federal and state statistical office, 2020). Agricultural landscapes in Brandenburg are characterised by large farm enterprises and large fields mostly arable, dominated by cereals and oilseeds (Amt für Statistik Berlin-Brandenburg, 2024; Gutzler et al., 2015). The agricultural production in the region faces challenges due to the high proportion of low-quality soils, i.e., mainly sandy and sandy-loamy soils, coupled with low rainfall and increasingly dry spring conditions exacerbated by climate change (Funk et al., 2023; Gutzler et al., 2015; Ihinegbu and Ogunwumi, 2022).

For our analysis we used a hexagonal grid within our study area with a resolution of 10 km², as this provides a uniform area unlike administrative areas that vary in shape and size. Following methods in Wolff et al. (2021), we defined these grid cells as "landscapes". To maintain consistency in hexagon size, we removed incomplete hexagons at Brandenburg's borders. As a result, 2757 hexagons out of a total of 3214 were retained for the analysis.

2.2. Defining landscape features and agricultural landscapes

Currently, as noted by Czúcz et al. (2022b), there is no comprehensive and consistent EU-wide definition of LF. The EU's Biodiversity Strategy refers to LF as "inter alia, buffer strips, rotational or non-rotational fallow land, hedges, non-productive trees, terrace walls, and ponds" yet the NRR describes them as "individual or group of trees, tree rows, field margins, patches, ditches, streams, small wetlands, terraces, cairns, stonewalls, small ponds and cultural features" (EU-COM, 2024b). Given the lack of alignment within the EU definitions, we used the LF definition proposed by Czúcz et al. (2022a) (see Section 1), which

is also used by the EU CAP Network Focus Group on “enhancing the biodiversity on farmland through high-diversity landscape features”, an EU-wide expert group working on the CAP. Based on the work by Czúcz et al. (2022a), we used four LF classes describing functional attributes – woody, grassy, wet, and stony features – and selected a set of thirteen frequently occurring and representative LF types for each class. Most of these have been also reflected in the CAP as GAEC, eco-schemes and rural development programmes (Czúcz et al., 2022b). For woody features, we selected hedges, shrubs, trees (isolated and in groups), tree lines and avenues, woody strips, riparian woody vegetation. For grassy features, we concentrated on grassy strips, field margins, and buffer strips. For wet features, we considered channels of fresh water and small water bodies, and for stony features we focused on dry stone walls and stacks of stones.

We conducted our analysis only in agricultural landscapes, which we defined as utilised agricultural area (UAA) that includes primary utilised arable area, permanent crops, grassland, and permanent pastures. We extracted UAA spatial data for Brandenburg from the 2022 IACS data and applied an automated cleaning procedure to remove erroneous geometries and topologies using R (Jänicke et al., 2022). Landscapes were classified as agricultural if at least 15 % of their area was UAA, a threshold chosen to represent substantial agricultural activity while excluding less impacted areas. This classification retained 2144 landscapes for analysis. We validated this definition by comparing different UAA thresholds (10 %, 15 %, 20 % and 25 %) using graphical and sensitivity analyses, with results detailed in Appendix A. The 15 % threshold was selected as it provided a balanced point, minimising significant changes in landscape classification while effectively capturing landscapes with considerable agricultural influence.

2.3. Methodological steps

2.3.1. Overview

We adopted a multi-scale approach to provide strategic spatial planning (EU-COM, 2019). At the landscape scale, we first assessed the current LF cover to establish a clearer understanding of the status quo (see Section 2.3.2). We then clustered and characterised the agricultural landscapes along a landscape complexity gradient (see Section 2.3.3). This clustering and characterisation approach allowed us to identify restoration priorities for the LF target based on not only the share of LF in the landscape but also the broader landscape composition and configuration. Since farmer’s acceptance and adoption are key barriers to LF restoration (Trujillo-Barrera et al., 2016; Wojtynia et al., 2023), we also focussed at the local level on identifying specific sites where LF could provide potential benefits to the farmer. These sites were within intensified, simple landscapes and had challenging management conditions, i. e., high erosion risk, and low productivity potential. We selected ten simple landscapes and demonstrated how sites located in the landscapes could be prioritised for LF restoration (see Section 2.3.4).

All analyses were carried out using R (version 4.2.0) and QGIS (version 3.28.0).

2.3.2. Landscape scale: assessing landscape feature cover

To comprehensively map LF in the agricultural landscapes and assess the LF cover per agricultural area (UAA), we created a new LF spatial dataset for Brandenburg, using three complementary datasets from which we extracted spatial data on the aforementioned LF classes and types (Table 1 and Appendix B): i) a digital (field) block register, which contained information on agricultural land eligible for CAP subsidies, from which we extracted the spatial information for all LF classes and types; ii) a digital landscape model, a nationwide standardised dataset, from which we extracted spatial data for the woody features LF class, alongside the resulting LF types; and iii) a habitat register, a standardised German-wide dataset from which we extracted data for all LF classes and types. For the habitat register dataset, we applied a threshold to exclude habitat patches larger than 0.5 ha, in contrast to the other two

Table 1
Considered datasets for LF cover assessment.

Variable	Name of dataset	Year	Source
Landscape features: Woody, grassy, wet and stony features	Digital (field) block register	2022	(Geobroker/LGB, 2022b)
Landscape features: Woody features	Woody Features in the digital landscape model	2022	(Geobroker/LGB, 2022a)
Landscape features: Woody, grassy, wet and stony features	Habitat register (areas)	2022	(LGB, 2022b)

datasets, which specifically digitise LF. This was done to avoid the “false” classification of larger (semi-)natural landscapes, such as grassland, as LF, following the guidelines suggested by Czúcz et al. (2022a). As there was some redundancy in the information contained within the datasets, we spatially intersected all datasets together to obtain a comprehensive and harmonised dataset of LF class and types in our study area. Whilst we note that information on LF are also available through EU’s IACS data to monitor CAP interventions and the Copernicus SWF dataset, we selected datasets that provide a more comprehensive LF dataset which cover those included in the IACS and SWF datasets.

2.3.3. Landscape scale: clustering agricultural landscapes

To characterise the agricultural landscapes, we clustered them using three ecologically relevant indicators that capture landscape complexity (Dufлот et al., 2015; Martin et al., 2019) namely, compositional heterogeneity, configurational heterogeneity, and landscape structure (Table 2). This built on previous regional studies focusing on farm and landscape characterisation for Brandenburg (e.g., Uthes and Kiesel, 2020; Venghaus and Acosta, 2018; Wolff et al., 2021) and complemented van der Zanden et al. (2016) approach which uses agricultural management intensity and landscape structure.

Compositional heterogeneity consisted of three metrics based on ecologically valuable semi-natural habitats: the percentage of UAA covered by i) LF, ii) forest, and iii) fallow land. Data for these variables was extracted from our newly collated LF dataset, the digital landscape model and from IACS data.

Configurational heterogeneity consisted of two metrics: (i) Perimeter-area ratio (PAR), calculated as the median PAR ratio for all field

Table 2
Overview of landscape indicators and corresponding metrics.

Landscape indicator	Landscape metrics	Calculation per landscape (unit)	Data source
Compositional heterogeneity	LF cover	LF cover per utilised agricultural area (%)	Newly collated LF dataset (see Section 2.3.2)
	Forest cover	Forest cover (%)	(Geobroker/LGB, 2022a)
	Fallow area cover	Fallow area cover (%)	(LGB 2022b)
Configurational heterogeneity	Perimeter-area ratio	Median of field block perimeter divided by field area (m^{-1})	(LGB 2022b)
	Shannon Diversity Index of a) LF classes b) LF types	Based on LF class and type classifications	Based on newly collated LF dataset classification (see Section 2.3.2)
Landscape structure	Field block size	Mean field block size (ha)	(LGB, 2022a)
	Agricultural area cover	Utilised agricultural area cover (%)	(LGB, 2022a)

blocks within each landscape using IACS data. Field blocks referred to continuous, usable and managed agricultural areas comprising one or more plots or fields; (ii) Shannon diversity of LF classes and LF types. We classified our newly collated LF dataset into the aforementioned four LF classes and thirteen LF types. For each agricultural landscape, we calculated the Shannon Diversity Index (SDI) to evaluate the diversity of both LF classes and types, based on the occurrence of specific LF classes and types within the landscape. We intentionally excluded crop types as a proxy for agrobiodiversity, following Hass et al. (2018) and Martin et al. (2019), as we considered their ecological importance to be lower than the other selected variables.

Landscape structure was assessed using two metrics: (i) the percentage cover of UAA per landscape and (ii) the average field block size, where each field block was assigned to a single agricultural landscape based on the location of its centroid (Wolff et al., 2021).

To classify agricultural landscapes using the metrics described above, we applied a hybrid clustering algorithm. To identify the most relevant variables for the clustering analysis, we first excluded those that were highly correlated ($p > 0.55$) based on Spearman's correlation coefficient (see Appendix C). Five variables remained which were used for the clustering analysis: percentage of LF, fallow area and agricultural area cover, SDI of LF classes and PAR. Using the selected five variables, we clustered the landscapes using a hybrid hierarchical k-means clustering analysis (R packages: *cluster* (Maechler et al., 2023), *factoextra* (Kassambara and Mundt, 2020)), which has been shown to achieve robust clustering results (Husson et al., 2017). We used a dendrogram analysis based on inter-cluster distances to find the optimal number of clusters and assessed model fit by calculating the silhouette coefficient (Kassambara, 2017). To characterise the clusters thereafter, we employed a comparative multi-level clustering approach. First, we calculated tertiles for the original nine landscape metrics for all agricultural landscapes. Second, clusters were classified by their average metric values to the corresponding tertile, categorising them as *low*, *moderate*, or *high*. For the landscape structure metrics, an inverted categorisation was used, as a high average field block size or agricultural area cover signified low landscape complexity. Using this approach, we categorised the subsequent landscape indicators based on the majority principle and named each cluster accordingly (see Appendix D).

To capture spatial autocorrelation among adjacent landscapes, we calculated the cluster joint count method (Plant, n.d.), focusing on each cluster. Following Wolff's et al. (2021) approach, we assigned a reference value of 1 to each cluster's joint count, with other clusters set to 0.

2.3.4. Local scale: exploring potential LF restoration sites

As the landscapes were clustered using ecological factors, we focused at the local scale on economic factors, i.e., perceived beneficial factors in this decision-making process (Massfeller et al., 2022). As there are many factors and considerations that can affect the choice of what to restore and where (see Section 4.3 Limitations and outlook), our exploration here serves as an initial framework toward the necessary adaption of EU aims to farm- and field-level decisions by farmers. Specifically, to address key economic factors that affect farmer's acceptance and uptake of LF measures, we identified sites that are challenging for agricultural production, centring around areas with low crop productivity potential (CPP) and high erosion risk (Garibaldi et al., 2023). This approach follows recommendations by Berger and Pfeffer (2011) and Trujillo-Barrera et al. (2016) and is similar to Holzkämper and Seppelt (2007) and Meyer et al. (2012). Converting these sites to LF is associated with lower short-term costs related to production losses, and possibly reducing risks and losses (e.g., due to erosion) making adoption more likely. To explore the approach of setting LF restoration priorities within landscapes, we used R to randomly select ten agricultural landscapes among those classified as intensively used, simple landscapes. Focusing on such landscapes has been proposed as highly ecologically effective (Le Clech et al., 2024; Tschardt et al., 2012). The selection of ten landscapes was designed to examine their variability in outcomes (% LF

cover reached) while keeping the scope manageable as an exploratory sample.

As a proxy for CPP, we used fieldscore data (e.g., Uthes and Kiesel, 2020; Wolff et al., 2021), a metric used to describe the quality of agricultural area based on factors such as soil fertility, drainage, and cultivation potential (LGB, 2022d). Lower values indicate areas with lower yield potential. Since Brandenburg has, on average, a relatively low CPP (Jacobs et al., 2018), we defined, based on expert opinions, challenging agricultural production sites as those with a CPP of less than 25. To identify high water erosion sites, we used data commonly used for determining flower-strips locations, which highlights areas affected by high water erosion (LGB, 2020). High wind erosion sites were classified as those falling within the top two hazard classes in the Brandenburg wind erosion layer (LGB, 2022c). To highlight the potential priority areas for LF restoration we intersected the areas with low CPP with the areas of high erosion risk (i.e., those with either high wind or water erosion), and assessed the total potential LF area that can be reached by this approach, i.e., by adding areas of "higher adoption potential" to existing ones.

3. Results

3.1. Landscape scale: assessing landscape feature cover

Our analysis of LF cover in Brandenburg indicated a low cover of LF in most agricultural landscapes; on average, LF cover was just 3.6 %. Further, 94.4 % of the considered agricultural landscapes had less than 10 % LF cover, 74.2 % of the agricultural landscapes had < 4 % LF cover and 18.9 % did not achieve more than 1 % (Fig. 1). Only 5.6 % (120 landscapes), totalling 120 km², exceeded 10 % LF cover, i.e., meeting the LF target.

3.2. Landscape scale: clustering agricultural landscapes

We identified five distinct agricultural landscape clusters in Brandenburg (Fig. 2. and Appendix E):

Cluster 1: simple agricultural landscapes of low compositional heterogeneity

These landscapes, covering 26 % of agricultural landscapes area (in total 567 landscapes), had the lowest landscape complexity in terms of both configurational and compositional heterogeneity. On average, agriculture covered 61.8 % of the total landscape. Average field block size was 9.2 ha (large compared to other landscape types in Brandenburg), and field margin density was low (average PAR = 0.026/m). Further, landscapes within this cluster had, on average, a low LF cover (2.1 %) and low diversity of LF types (SDI type: $9.6 \cdot 10^{-8}$). Average forest and fallow area cover were 23 % and 1.1 %, respectively.

Cluster 2: simple agricultural landscapes of moderate heterogeneity

Accounting for 30.5 % of the considered landscapes, i.e., 654 landscapes in total, this cluster had the highest agricultural cover (on average 67.9 % of the landscape area) and the largest field block size among the clusters (average size = 10.7 ha). However, field margin density in this cluster was, on average, comparatively low (PAR = 0.03/m). In contrast to Cluster 1, LF cover was slightly higher, with an average of 2.2 %.

Cluster 3: moderate complex agricultural landscapes

Comprising 7.8 % of the considered landscapes (corresponding to 168 landscapes), Cluster 3 had a slightly lower agricultural cover (50 %) and a moderate level of heterogeneity, characterised by moderate values of LF diversity (SDI class: $5.38 \cdot 10^{-6}$; SDI type: $1.23 \cdot 10^{-8}$), field margin density (average PAR = 0.03/m), and average coverage of LF (2.9 %) and forest (27.8 %). Notably, landscape within this cluster exhibited the highest proportion of fallow areas, with an average of 7 %.

Cluster 4: mosaic landscapes of moderate heterogeneity

Covering 1.9 % of the landscapes considered, i.e., in total 41 landscapes, landscapes within Cluster 4 showed, on average, even lower

Fig. 1. Percentage landscape feature cover of agricultural landscapes across Brandenburg, Germany.

overall agricultural cover (24.9 %) and smaller field block sizes (average = 5.5 ha). They also had a high average cover of semi-natural areas, namely LF (29.7 %) and forest (33.7 %), yet fallow area (1.3 %) was lower than Cluster 3 which corresponds with the lower agricultural area cover found in this cluster. Although Cluster 4 contained a high cover of semi-natural areas, both configurational and compositional heterogeneity remained at a moderate level, characterised, among others, by a low LF diversity for both classes (SDI class: $3.4 \cdot 10^{-8}$) and types (SDI type: $9.3 \cdot 10^{-8}$).

Cluster 5: complex mosaic landscapes

This cluster constituted 33.3 % of the considered landscapes (equalling 714), and was characterised by a mix of land cover and a high degree of overall complexity. Landscapes within this cluster had a relatively low proportion of agricultural cover (average = 34.6 % of the area), and the smallest field block sizes (average = 5.4 ha). The complexity in this cluster was primarily due to its high configurational heterogeneity, driven by a high coverage of LF (4.7 %), forest (43.3 %), and to a lesser extent fallow land (0.9 %). Further, the configurational complexity within Cluster 5 was marked by a moderate diversity of LF types and classes (SDI class: $6.28 \cdot 10^{-8}$; SDI type: $1.32 \cdot 10^{-7}$) as well as a high average field margin density (0.04/m).

The aforementioned clusters describe a gradient of landscape complexity from simple landscapes (Clusters 1 and 2), through moderate complex landscapes (Cluster 3) to mosaic and complex mosaic landscapes (Cluster 4 and 5, respectively). All landscapes meeting the LF target, i.e., with a LF cover above 10 %, were found in Cluster 4 and 5.

Using hybrid clustering and joint-count analysis, we found significant spatial autocorrelation among the five landscape clusters (see Appendix F), indicating geographic clustering.

3.3. Local scale: exploring potential LF restoration sites

The ten randomly selected landscapes were, on average, characterised by an UAA cover of 69.3 % (± 15.6 %) and a LF cover of 1.6 % (± 1.1 %). Areas with low CPP covered, on average, 19.2 % of the UAA (± 19.3 %), while the areas at high risk of wind erosion and water erosion covered, on average, 44.1 % (± 34.8 %) and 1.3 % (± 1.2 %) out of the UAA, respectively (for further details see Appendix G). Areas that met both criteria, i.e., the intersection of low fieldscore and high erosion risk, covered on average 11.3 % of the UAA (± 18.8 %). Thus, if chosen as priority areas for LF restoration, would provide substantial area for almost all landscapes that could be used to increase the LF share in that area (see Table G1 in Appendix G).

We exemplify this approach for a single agricultural landscape in Fig. 3. This landscape had low CPP (10.4 %), and a high wind (93.5 %), and water erosion risk (2.5 %) across its agricultural area. After intersecting areas of low CPP and high erosion, we identified 4.7 % of UAA area as potential LF restoration sites, which would add to the existing LF cover of 0.8 %.

Fig. 2. Agricultural landscape clusters in Brandenburg.

4. Discussion

4.1. Contributing to the EU Biodiversity Strategy 10 % landscape feature target

4.1.1. How far are we from the 10 % LF target?

In this study we explored how data could be compiled, and analyses conducted, to approach the challenging task of mapping and prioritising LF restoration toward the target of reaching 10 % coverage of landscape features on agricultural areas. We explored the approach for the federal state of Brandenburg, a region characterised by high agricultural coverage. Our analysis indicated a remarkably low LF cover in Brandenburg's agricultural landscapes, with 94.4 % of landscapes falling short of the EU Biodiversity Strategy's LF target for 2030. In fact, even if the CAP's requirement for GAEC 8 was fully used to set a strict standard of 4 % LF cover, 74.2 % of the agricultural landscapes would still fall short. Reaching the 10 % LF target is therefore, for some regions, clearly a real challenge. A previous national assessment of LF cover across Germany found LF covered only 2.85 % of UAA (Czúcz et al., 2022a). In comparison, our findings indicate a slightly higher LF coverage of 3.6 % LF in Brandenburg. This discrepancy may stem from the use of different datasets and calculation methods.

Whilst the LF target aims to promote "high-diversity LF", this term so far lacks a standardised definition. We propose categorising LF classes and types based on Czúcz et al. (2022a); and quantifying LF diversity using the Shannon Diversity Index. Considering both the diversity of LF types and LF classes is critical, as this ensures the consideration of a

range of niches that meet the varied habitat requirements and ecological conditions needed by different farmland species. Using this approach, our findings reveal that 28.4 % of clustered landscapes in Brandenburg exhibit low LF diversity (Clusters 1 and 4). Notably, even the other clusters only showed moderate LF diversity on average – indicating that initially high investments by governments at different levels may be required to support farmers not only in enhancing LF cover but also LF diversity. These initial investments and potential costs could be justified, to some extent, by the substantial long-term benefits of LF through their contribution to soil erosion and flood protection, water filtration, carbon sequestration, biodiversity and cultural values.

4.1.2. How to set priorities for restoration?

Setting priorities for restoration is primarily a political exercise where the outcome depends on the defined aims and motivations at the EU, national and federal levels – but it should be informed by both ecological and socioeconomic criteria. From a landscape ecology perspective, research on landscape moderation suggests that given their potential for increasing complexity, simple landscapes should be prioritised for restoration (Marja et al., 2019, 2022; Tschamtkte et al., 2005, 2012, 2021), with the consideration of both landscape structure as well as compositional and configurational landscape heterogeneity (e.g., Martin et al., 2019; Weissteiner et al., 2016). For this, we suggest focusing on increasing the overall complexity of the landscape, alongside boosting both the cover and diversity of LF, the field margin density (i.e., enhance field complexity and restoring smaller field sizes; Haddad et al., 2015; Tschamtkte et al., 2021), and restoring additional

Fig. 3. Utilised agricultural areas in our selected landscape which had (A) low crop productivity potential and (B) high wind and water erosion risk. These maps were intersected to show the potential areas for LF restoration.

semi-natural habitats (e.g., forest or fallow area; Batáry et al., 2011; Dufлот et al., 2015). Our landscape clustering method allows for deriving targeted recommendations on how regional planners, farmers and administrators can link landscape characteristics to specific measures to restore LF and enhance landscape complexity, particularly focusing on Cluster 1 and 2. For Cluster 1, this would involve enhancing LF diversity, followed by increasing LF cover and boosting field margin density. In Cluster 2, the emphasis would be on restoring semi-natural habitats, such as forests and woods, followed by fallow area, while also boosting field margin density. In addition, the protection and improved management of the existing semi-natural area and LF should be emphasised (see Section 4.1.3). However, it is important to acknowledge that in real-world landscapes, different objectives and motivations must be balanced out (see Section 4.2).

At the local scale, since we have focused on areas of high erosion risk and low production potential, we advise adding grassy or woody features, such as buffer strips or hedges, that can reduce the erosion risk and improve soil fertility as well as multiple other benefits (Holland et al., 2017). These benefits need to be better communicated with farmers and land-owners, to enhance acceptance and adoption of measures (Geertsema et al., 2016; Kakabadse et al., 2007). However, as outlined above, the decision of which LF type is ecologically most appropriate and acceptable for farmers is influenced by a range of factors such as technical conditions, property rights, topography and typical wind directions. Furthermore, the distinct LF types exhibit considerable differences in their planting requirements, management practices, public funding and therefore their costs. Hedges, for instance, are costlier than field margins, though costs can vary highly even within LF types (see for example the Bavarian cost calculator for hedges; Bayerisches Landesamt für Umwelt, n.d.) (Baumland Kampagne, 2024; Beiersdorf, 2022). Our approach is therefore intended to be used as a starting point that should be further co-developed with farmers and other relevant actors, taking into consideration their knowledge, interests, priorities, to ultimately create an appropriate management plan for LF. A critical aspect in this process would be therefore to address implementation, opportunity and transaction costs resulting from reduced cropping areas, and increased

field management expenses which can vary from area to area and across different LF classes and types. With further development, our approach aims to foster collaborative decision-making and knowledge exchange, both in restoration and improved management of LF. This is crucial to the successful establishment and maintenance of LF (EU-COM, 2019).

4.1.3. Beyond the 10 % LF target: considering complex landscapes

Focusing restoration efforts on simple landscapes can deliver efficient outcomes, maximising biodiversity gains relative to the investment (Le Clech et al., 2024; Tscharnatke et al., 2012). However, in some regions such a focus may benefit primarily common and generalist species (Bengtsson, 2009; Tscharnatke et al., 2005). Given the rapid declines among common species (Batáry et al., 2017; Bowler et al., 2019; van Klink et al., 2020, 2024), this approach sets adequate priorities for simple landscapes. However, complex landscapes that encompass a high diversity of habitats and species, including habitat specialists, must not be overlooked. Securing good management, and potentially restoring missing LF in these landscapes, may be essential for promoting a functioning and healthy ecosystem. Accordingly, while this study aims to support the political LF target, which explicitly focuses on simpler landscapes (implicitly, Clusters 1 and 2), the landscape metrics used in our clustering approach can also be used to derive recommendations for a broader range of landscape types (Clusters 3–5). This is particularly important given that various studies suggest that the 10 % LF target may not be sufficient for many species and ecological processes (e.g., Garibaldi et al., 2021). Further, whilst our proposed local level prioritisation approach considers mostly socioeconomic and agronomic conditions, we wish to emphasise that restoration and conservation efforts should not be limited to simpler landscapes, or to areas of low productivity or erosion risks alone. Rather, complementary criteria may need to further develop new and possibly complementary prioritisation approaches, which, in the short term, may involve higher opportunity costs (e.g., reduced agricultural yields) and require appropriate compensation mechanisms to reflect the value of public goods provided.

4.2. Usefulness of the methodology

In our proposed methodology we utilised several relevant datasets to assess current LF cover. Whilst these specific datasets were standardised for Germany (e.g., digital landscape model or habitat register), they are also available at the EU level in an identical or similar format (i.e. covered in IACS and Land Parcel Identification System (LPIS) data for the CAP funding and habitat register for assessments for the Birds, Habitats and Water Framework Directives). This standardisation facilitates the potential transferability of our methods to other German or European regions, to support regional planners, farmers and administrators in assessing the status quo of LF, aiding in prioritizing efforts and budget-allocation, and possibly also supporting policymakers in streamlining LF objectives, indicators and monitoring. Ultimately, this approach can also provide farmers with a clearer understanding of how the measures taken on their farms contribute to larger-scale benefits in surrounding landscapes, as an inspiration for starting the LF planning and restoration. Further, whilst we choose specific datasets, our methodology is flexible enough to also be able to incorporate alternative datasets to accommodate different restoration aims.

At present, our method considers a limited set of criteria based on two NCPs which were selected for their high relevance in our study region: agricultural production potential and soil erosion mitigation risk. The approach aims to improve acceptance by farmers, as it is meant to serve as a starting point for communication and discussion with farmers. The criteria considered can, and should, be expanded in future applications to better reflect the problems and priorities identified across specific regions and landscapes. For instance, this could include consideration of other metrics of “success”, which may include additional locally relevant NCPs and consider dimensions of technical and agronomic feasibility, topographical, edaphic, and ecological conditions (Bennett, 2017; Holzkämper and Seppelt, 2007; Meyer et al., 2012; Polasky et al., 2005), socioeconomic, cultural and administrative context (Danijel et al., 2024), and people’s preferences (Frank et al., 2022; Geertsema et al., 2016).

4.3. Limitations and outlook

Our study incorporated a range of data sources to assess LF as comprehensively as possible, focusing on agricultural landscapes in Brandenburg as a case study. The approach aims to support administrators and planners in overcoming current limitations linked to an absence of standardised EU-wide LF datasets. However, it comes with certain limitations at the landscape scale: first, depending on the LF dataset, it may be difficult to develop a fully comprehensive LF dataset due to data gaps. Even in our case, we cannot guarantee that our dataset encompasses all LF. Second, our usage of the SDI may not reflect the entire spectrum of “high-diversity LF” classes or types due to the index’s sensitivity to richness and evenness, as well as threshold effects, wherein rare, yet ecologically important, LF classes or types might not have been adequately reflected. Third, due to a lack of data, we were not able to include the quality of the LF in our approach which could provide another approach to assess high-diversity LF, i.e., high quality habitats.

The range of potential LF priority sites at the local scale indicates that this approach is sufficient for some landscapes and provides good options for identifying LF sites. However, for a few landscapes, an insufficient area is highlighted for LF restoration. In addition, in highly productive agricultural regions or areas with minimal erosion risk, our proposed local scale approach may have little value. As mentioned, identifying LF sites is a complex decision-making process that can be only partially addressed with our current criteria selection. Therefore, our approach can be used as a starting point to discuss the incorporation of additional criteria addressing the regional variability across European landscapes, capturing the specific needs of farmers and stakeholders, and considering synergies and trade-offs of NCPs.

It is important to acknowledge that the role of this paper is not to

assess the LF target but rather to explore, and advance the methodologies, for its potential implementation. Setting the specific target or priorities, in accordance with the EU’s Biodiversity Strategy LF target – as well as the NRR and CAP as implementation instruments – is rather a political benchmark which ignores the inherent variations in social, economic, and biophysical conditions across agricultural landscapes in the EU and beyond. These variations, combined with a reluctance of farmers and landowners to restore LF, requires a pragmatic approach for translating EU-level targets, through national- and subnational-level guidance for administrators, into local-level priorities that can support farmers and landowners to adopt often hard-to-accept measures. This paper therefore advances the methods that are needed for prioritising efforts and delivering specifications for land managers. We believe that our presented methodology has the potential to support decision makers in overcoming the barriers of interpreting and implementing the LF target based on available data and a scientifically grounded understanding of landscape-level agroecological processes.

5. Conclusion and policy recommendations

Overall, we propose a locally adaptable and policy-oriented methodology that leverages data available for all EU Member States, enabling its adoption throughout Europe and thus, supporting Member States in aligning with the LF target. However, during the process of data collection, standardisation, and analysis, we identified several challenges for achieving the LF target. In the following section, we summarise the key policy implications and recommendations for addressing these challenges.

A) Setting clear definitions & clarifying targets

The lack of a clear definition for “high-diversity LF” and “agricultural areas”, and the appropriate scale for implementing the LF target, jeopardises its successful conversion into actionable, on-the-ground results. Whilst in this current study we have used particular definitions for these two terms and proposed a scale at which to assess them, it is imperative that the EU Commission provides guidance through definitive and comprehensive definitions, to ensure the effective restoration, management and protection of LF across the Member States.

B) Determining concrete measures for implementation and monitoring

A major challenge for evaluating the status, trends, and gaps in LF cover arises from poor and inconsistent LF data. This can hinder Member States from reporting how they identified and prioritised landscapes for restoration. A clearer definition of concrete measures that Member States need to take with regards to mapping LF is therefore essential for effective monitoring.

To produce the relevant data needed for effective planning and implementation, we recommend the creation of a standardised EU-wide protocol for data collection and the mapping, reporting, and monitoring of LF which aligns with the FAIR Principles (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable). Additionally, we support extending the CAP’s LPIS to cover entire farms, not just the areas supported by the CAP, as is currently done (Pe’er et al., 2022). This could be done, for instance, by simplifying the current system where farmers apply separately for support by different CAP instruments, to a whole farm support scheme facilitated by whole farm mapping which includes non-eligible areas. Moreover, mapping of LF is needed also for farms and other areas beyond those seeking CAP support. Building on existing reporting systems, combining satellite-based remote sensing mapping with targeted *in-situ* mapping, could vastly improve the comprehensiveness and reliability of LF mapping and monitoring.

C) Ensuring funding for implementation and maintenance

To meet the *LF target*, establishing attractive incentives for farmers and other land managers and owners will be crucial. Here, Member States should ensure sufficient funding options. While several CAP instruments, particularly AECM and non-productive investment measures, could be leveraged toward this aim, Member States will need to explore how to better utilise existing and new instruments in and beyond the CAP. To this end, we recommend Member States first enhance CAP funding schemes that are specifically focused on LF. Additionally, Natura 2000 payments and other regional funds could support to expand funding opportunities for farmers and other land managers and owners who require compensation for investments or losses.

D) Engaging local actors for successful implementation and monitoring

Engaging relevant local actors in participatory processes may help to bridge the gap between agroecological principles and existing knowledge. This co-creation and knowledge-sharing approach can enhance the successful adoption of measures by those responsible for implementing them. To further improve acceptance, it is essential to increase education and awareness of the benefits of LF restoration. Additionally, integrating large-scale landowners, such as communities, cities, and churches, will be pivotal in scaling up restoration efforts. Exploring the ways to generate benefits for participating farmers, and bringing everyone on board, remains both a challenge and an opportunity to explore.

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Authors contributions

LNS, ACW, VSB, SDBK, EAF and GP conceived the ideas and designed methodology; LNS collected and analysed the data; LNS, EAF and GP led the writing of the manuscript. ACW, VSB, SDBK and AB pre-reviewed the manuscript. All co-authors contributed to the manuscript.

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Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Appendix A. Supporting information

Supplementary data associated with this article can be found in the online version at [doi:10.1016/j.landusepol.2025.107531](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.landusepol.2025.107531).

Data availability

Information on the data used is available in the Appendix. The computational notebook and the generated dataset of landscape features have been published in Zenodo (Schaan, 2025a, 2025b).

References

- Amt für Statistik Berlin-Brandenburg, 2024. Ausgewählte Ergebnisse der Agrarstrukturerhebung im Land Berlin 2023. Amt für Statistik Berlin-Brandenburg.
- Batáry, P., Báldi, A., Kleijn, D., Tschamtké, T., 2011. Landscape-moderated biodiversity effects of agri-environmental management: a meta-analysis. *Proc. R. Soc. B Biol. Sci.* 278 (1713), 1894–1902. <https://doi.org/10.1098/RSPB.2010.1923>.
- Batáry, P., Gallé, R., Riesch, F., Fischer, C., Dormann, C.F., Mußhoff, O., Császár, P., Fusaro, S., Gayler, C., Happe, A.-K., Kurucz, K., Molnár, D., Rösch, V., Wietzke, A., Tschamtké, T., 2017. The former Iron Curtain still drives biodiversity–profit trade-offs in German agriculture. *Nat. Ecol. Evol.* 1 (9), 1279–1284. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41559-017-0272-x>.
- Batáry, P., Matthiesen, T., Tschamtké, T., 2010. Landscape-moderated importance of hedges in conserving farmland bird diversity of organic vs. Conventional croplands and grasslands. *Biol. Conserv.* 143 (9), 2020–2027. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biocon.2010.05.005>.
- Baumland Kampagne, 2024. BaumLand-Förderübersicht “Hecken.” Förderverein Arbeitsgemeinschaft bäuerliche Landwirtschaft e.V.
- Bayerisches Landesamt für Umwelt, n.d. Arbeitshilfen zur Kostendatei – allgemeine Hinweise und Kurzanleitung.
- Beiersdorf, H., 2022. *Kostendatei für Maßnahmen des Naturschutzes und der Landschaftspflege (UmweltSpezial)*. Bayer. Landesamt F. üR. Umw.
- Belfrage, K., Björklund, J., Salomonsson, L., 2015. Effects of farm size and on-farm landscape heterogeneity on biodiversity—case study of twelve farms in a Swedish Landscape. *Agroecol. Sustain. Food Syst.* 39 (2), 170–188. <https://doi.org/10.1080/21683565.2014.967437>.
- Bengtsson, J., 2009. Chapter 9 Applied (meta)community ecology: diversity and ecosystem services at the intersection of local and regional processes. *Community Ecol. Process. Models Appl.* <https://doi.org/10.1093/ACPROF:OSO/9780199228973.003.0010>, 9780199228973.
- Bennett, E.M., 2017. Changing the agriculture and environment conversation. *Nat. Ecol. Evol.* 1 (1). <https://doi.org/10.1038/S41559-016-0018>.
- Berger, G., Pfeffer, H., 2011. Naturschutzbrachen im Ackerbau Praxishandbuch für die Anlage und optimierte Bewirtschaftung kleinflächiger Lebensräume für die biologische Vielfalt (https://books.google.com/books/about/Naturschutzbrachen_im_Ackerbau.html?id=7SQstwAACAAJ).
- Blanco, J., Sourdril, A., Deconchat, M., Barnaud, C., San Cristobal, M., Andrieu, E., 2020. How farmers feel about trees: perceptions of ecosystem services and disservices associated with rural forests in southwestern France. *Ecosyst. Serv.* 42, 101066. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecoser.2020.101066>.
- Blüthgen, N., Dicks, L.V., Forister, M.L., Outhwaite, C.L., Slade, E.M., 2023. Insect declines in the Anthropocene. *Nat. Rev. Earth Environ.* 4 (10), 683–686. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s43017-023-00478-x>.
- Bowler, D., Heldbjerg, H., Fox, A.D., de Jong, M., Böhning-Gaese, K., 2019. Long-term declines of European insectivorous bird populations and potential causes. *Conserv. Biol.* 33 (5), 1120–1130. <https://doi.org/10.1111/cobi.13307>.
- Calvin, K., Dasgupta, D., Krinner, G., Mukherji, A., Thorne, P.W., Trisos, C., Romero, J., Aldunce, P., Barrett, K., Blanco, G., Cheung, W.W.L., Connors, S., Denton, F., Diongue-Niang, A., Dodman, D., Garschagen, M., Geden, O., Hayward, B., Jones, C., Péan, C., 2023. *Climate change 2023: synthesis report*. (First). Intergov. Panel Clim. Change (IPCC). <https://doi.org/10.59327/IPCC/AR6-9789291691647>.
- Castro Campos, B., 2022. The rules-boundaries-behaviours (RBB) framework for farmers' adoption decisions of sustainable agricultural practices. *J. Rural Stud.* 92, 164–179. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jrurstud.2022.03.012>.

- Czúcz, B., Baruth, B., Terres, J. M., Gallego, J., Hagyo, A., Angileri, V., Nocita, M., Perez Soba, M., Koebler, R., Paracchini, M., 2022a. *Classification and quantification of landscape features in agricultural land across the EU*. European Commission. Joint Research Centre.
- Czúcz, B., Baruth, B., Angileri, V., Prieto Lopez, A., Hagyo, A., Terres, J. M., 2022b. *Landscape features in the EU Member States: A review of existing data and approaches*. European Commission. Joint Research Centre.
- Dainese, M., Martin, E.A., Aizen, M.A., Albrecht, M., Bartomeus, I., Bommarco, R., Carvalheiro, L.G., Chaplin-Kramer, R., Gagic, V., Garibaldi, L.A., Ghazoul, J., Grab, H., Jonsson, M., Karp, D.S., Kennedy, C.M., Kleijn, D., Kremen, C., Landis, D. A., Letourneau, D.K., Steffan-Dewenter, I., 2019. A global synthesis reveals biodiversity-mediated benefits for crop production. *Sci. Adv.* 5 (10). https://doi.org/10.1126/SCIENCE.AAX0121/SUPPL_FILE/AAX0121_SM.PDF.
- Danijel, I., Nataša, P., Jaša, G.V., Daša, D., Mitja, K., Sonja, Š., Igor, Ž., Jure, Č., Petra, R. N., Štefan, K., Matej, B., Damjan, S., 2024. A decision support system for effective implementation of agro-environmental measures targeted at small woody landscape features: the case study of Slovenia. *Landsc. Urban Plan.* 247, 105064. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.landurbplan.2024.105064>.
- De Stefano, A., Jacobson, M.G., 2018. Soil carbon sequestration in agroforestry systems: a meta-analysis. *Agrofor. Syst.* 92 (2), 285–299. <https://doi.org/10.1007/S10457-017-0147-9>.
- Dockès, A.-C., Chauvat, S., Correa, P., Turlot, A., Nettle, R., 2019. Advice and advisory roles about work on farms. A review. *Agron. Sustain. Dev.* 39 (1), 2. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13593-018-0547-x>.
- Duflot, R., Aviron, S., Ernout, A., Fahrig, L., Burel, F., 2015. Reconsidering the role of 'semi-natural habitat' in agricultural landscape biodiversity: a case study. *Ecol. Res.* 30 (1), 75–83. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12884-014-1211-9>.
- EU CAP Network, n.d. Focus Group-Enhancing the biodiversity on farmland through high-diversity landscape features—Final report.
- EU, 2020. EU Biodiversity Strategy for 2030 Bringing nature back into our lives. In COM (2020) 380 final. (<https://ec.europa.eu/research/environment/index.cfm?pg=nbs>).
- EU-COM, 2024a. European farmers exempted from rules on land lying fallow [Press release]. (https://ec.europa.eu/commission/presscorner/detail/en/IP_24_781).
- EU-COM, 2024b. Regulation (EU) 2024/1991 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 24 June 2024 on nature restoration and amending Regulation (EU) 2022/869. (<http://data.europa.eu/eli/reg/2024/1991/oj>).
- EU-COM, 2019. EU guidance on integrating ecosystems and their services into decision-making (Commission Staff Working Document SWD(2019) 305 final).
- Federal and state statistical office., 2020. Agricultural structure survey/agricultural census (Code: 41141).
- Frank, M., Amoroso, M.M., Propedo, M., Kaufmann, B., 2022. Co-inquiry in agroecology research with farmers: transdisciplinary co-creation of contextualized and actionable knowledge. *Agroecol. Sustain. Food Syst.* 46 (4), 510–539. <https://doi.org/10.1080/21683565.2021.2020948>.
- Funk, R., Völker, L., Deumlich, D., 2023. Landscape structure model based estimation of the wind erosion risk in Brandenburg, Germany. *Aeolian Res.* 62. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.aeolia.2023.100878>.
- Garau, E., Pueyo-Ros, J., Jiménez-Aceituno, A., Peterson, G., Norström, A., Ribas Palom, A., Vila-Subirós, J., 2023. Landscape features shape people's perception of ecosystem service supply areas. *Ecosyst. Serv.* 64. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecoser.2023.101561>.
- Garibaldi, L.A., Oddi, F.J., Miguez, F.E., Bartomeus, I., Orr, M.C., Jobbágy, E.G., Kremen, C., Schulte, L.A., Hughes, A.C., Bagnato, C., Abramson, G., Bridgewater, P., Carella, D.G., Díaz, S., Dicks, L.V., Ellis, E.C., Goldenberg, M., Huaylla, C.A., Kuperman, M., Zhu, C.D., 2021. Working landscapes need at least 20% native habitat. *Zerv. Lett.* 14 (2), e12773. <https://doi.org/10.1111/CONL.12773>.
- Garibaldi, L.A., Zermoglio, P.F., Jobbágy, E.G., Andreoni, L., Ortiz de Urbina, A., Grass, I., Oddi, F.J., 2023. How to design multifunctional landscapes? *J. Appl. Ecol.* 60 (12), 2521–2527. <https://doi.org/10.1111/1365-2664.14517>.
- Geertsema, W., Rossing, W.A., Landis, D.A., Bianchi, F.J., Van Rijn, P.C., Schaminée, J. H., Tschamtker, T., Van Der Werf, W., 2016. Actionable knowledge for ecological intensification of agriculture. *Front. Ecol. Environ.* 14 (4), 209–216. <https://doi.org/10.1002/fee.1258>.
- Geobroker/LGB., 2022a. Digitales Basis-Landschaftsmodell. (<https://geobroker.geobasis-bb.de/gbss.php?MODE=GetProductInformation&PRODUCTID=d2ea212-f68d-4e2-d-a7e7-8e8063d1b855>).
- Geobroker/LGB., 2022b. Digitales Feldblockkataster. (<https://geobroker.geobasis-bb.de/gbss.php?MODE=GetProductInformation&PRODUCTID=9e95f21f-4ecf-4682-9a44-e5f7609f6fa0>).
- Goggins, G., Zurbrügg, C., Todorovic, S.K., & Moosmann, S., 2023. EU CAP Network LF: The role of knowledge and promotion.
- Golicz, K., Ghazaryan, G., Niether, W., Wartenberg, A.C., Breuer, L., Gatterer, A., Jacobs, S.R., Kleinebecker, T., Weckenbrock, P., Große-Stoltenberg, A., 2021. The role of small woody landscape features and agroforestry systems for national carbon budgeting in Germany. *Land* 10 (10). <https://doi.org/10.3390/land10101028>.
- Gregory, R.D., Skoropilova, J., Vorisek, P., Butler, S., 2019. An analysis of trends, uncertainty and species selection shows contrasting trends of widespread forest and farmland birds in Europe. *Ecol. Indic.* 103, 676–687. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecolind.2019.04.064>.
- Gutzler, C., Helming, K., Balla, D., Dannowski, R., Deumlich, D., Glennitz, M., Knierim, A., Mirschel, W., Nendel, C., Paul, C., Sieber, S., Stachow, U., Starick, A., Wieland, R., Wurbs, A., Zander, P., 2015. Agricultural land use changes—a scenario-based sustainability impact assessment for Brandenburg, Germany. *Ecol. Indic.* 48, 505–517. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecolind.2014.09.004>.
- Haddad, N.M., Brudvig, L.A., Clobert, J., Davies, K.F., Gonzalez, A., Holt, R.D., Lovejoy, T.E., Sexton, J.O., Austin, M.P., Collins, C.D., Cook, W.M., Damschen, E.I., Ewers, R.M., Foster, B.L., Jenkins, C.N., King, A.J., Laurance, W.F., Levey, D.J., Margules, C.R., Townshend, J.R., 2015. Habitat fragmentation and its lasting impact on Earth's ecosystems. *Sci. Adv.* 1 (2), e1500052. <https://doi.org/10.1126/sciadv.1500052>.
- Hass, A.L., Kormann, U.G., Tschamtker, T., Clough, Y., Baillo, A.B., Sirami, C., Fahrig, L., Martin, J.L., Baudry, J., Bertrand, C., Bosch, J., Brotons, L., Bure, F., Georges, R., Giralt, D., Marcos-García, M., Ricarte, A., Siritwardena, G., Batáry, P., 2018. Landscape configurational heterogeneity by small-scale agriculture, not crop diversity, maintains pollinators and plant reproduction in western Europe. *Proc. R. Soc. B Biol. Sci.* 285 (1872). <https://doi.org/10.1098/rspb.2017.2242>.
- 2019a HLP.E., 2019. Agroecological and other innovative approaches for sustainable agriculture and food systems that enhance food security and nutrition. A report by the High-Level Panel of Experts on Food Security and Nutrition of the Committee on World Food Security. FAO. (www.fao.org/cfs/cfs-hlpe).
- Holland, J.M., Douma, J.C., Crowley, L., James, L., Kor, L., Stevenson, D.R.W., Smith, B. M., 2017. Semi-natural habitats support biological control, pollination and soil conservation in Europe. A review. *Agron. Sustain. Dev.* 37 (4). <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13593>.
- Holzschläger, A., Seppelt, R., 2007. Evaluating cost-effectiveness of conservation management actions in an agricultural landscape on a regional scale. *Biol. Conserv.* 136 (1), 117–127. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biocon.2006.11.011>.
- Husson, F., Le, S., & Pagès, J., 2017. Exploratory Multivariate Analysis by Example Using R. (https://books.google.de/books?hl=en&l_r=&id=nLR0DGAQAQBAJ&oi=fnd&pg=PP1&dq=Exploratory+Multivariate+Analysis+by+Example+Using+R&ots=ba9R6Tz5cJ&sig=iw2DFkg9Lp-C9w6rBCID9d4zw&redir_esc=y#v=onepage&q=Exploratory%20Multivariate%20Analysis%20by%20Example%20Using%20R&f=false).
- Ihnegbu, C., Ogunwumi, T., 2022. Multi-criteria modelling of drought: a study of Brandenburg Federal State, Germany. *Model. Earth Syst. Environ.* 8 (2), 2035–2049. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s40808-021-01197-2>.
- IPBES., 2019a. Global assessment report of the Intergovernmental Science-Policy Platform on Biodiversity and Ecosystem Services. Intergovernmental Science-Policy Platform on Biodiversity and Ecosystem Services (IPBES).
- IPBES., 2019b. Summary for policymakers of the IPBES global assessment report on biodiversity and ecosystem services. (www.ipbes.net).
- Jacobs, A., Flessa, H., Don, A., Heidkamp, A., Prietz, R., Dechow, R., Gensior, A., Poeplau, C., Riggers, C., Schneider, F., Tiemeyer, B., Vos, C., Wittnebel, M., Müller, T., Säurich, A., Fahrion-Nitschke, A., Gebbert, S., Hopfstock, R., Jaconi, A., Freibauer, A., 2018. *Landwirtschaftlich genutzte Böden in Deutschland: Ergebnisse der Bodenzustandserhebung* (Thünen Report). Johann Heinrich von Thünen-Inst.
- Jänicke, C., Goddard, A., Stein, S., Steinmann, H.H., Lakes, T., Nendel, C., Müller, D., 2022. Field-level land-use data reveal heterogeneous crop sequences with distinct regional differences in Germany. *Eur. J. Agron.* 141, 126632. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.eja.2022.126632>.
- Kakabadse, N.K., Kakabadse, A.P., Kalu, K.N., 2007. Communicative Action through Collaborative Inquiry: journey of a Facilitating Co-Inquirer. *Syst. Pract. Action Res.* 20 (3), 245–272. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11213-006-9061-1>.
- Kassambara, A., Mundt, F., 2020. factoextra: extract and visualize the results of multivariate data analyses [Computer software]. *Compr. R. Arch. Netw. (CRAN)*. (<https://CRAN.R-project.org/package=factoextra>).
- Kassambara, A., 2017. Practical Guide to Cluster Analysis in R. Unsupervised Machine Learning. (<http://www.sthda.com>).
- Klebl, F., Feindt, P.H., Piore, A., 2024. Farmers' behavioural determinants of on-farm biodiversity management in Europe: a systematic review. *Agric. Hum. Values* 41 (2), 831–861. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10460-023-10505-8>.
- Kleijn, D., Baquero, R.A., Clough, Y., Díaz, M., De Esteban, J., Fernández, F., Gabriel, D., Herzog, F., Holzschuh, A., Jöhl, R., Knop, E., Kruess, A., Marshall, E.J.P., Steffan-Dewenter, I., Tschamtker, T., Verhulst, J., West, T.M., Yela, J.L., 2006. Mixed biodiversity benefits of agri-environment schemes in five European countries. *Ecol. Lett.* 9 (3), 243–254. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1461-0248.2005.00869.x>.
- Klunnert, A., Barbosa, A.L., Catarino, R., Fellmann, T., Baldoni, E., Beber, C., Hristov, J., Paracchini, M.L., Rega, C., Weiss, F., Witzke, P., Rodriguez-Cerezo, E., 2024. Landscape features support natural pest control and farm income when pesticide application is reduced. *Nat. Commun.* 15 (1). <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41467-024-48311-3>.
- Lajos, K., Császár, O., Sárospataki, M., Samu, F., Tóth, F., 2020. Linear woody landscape elements may help to mitigate leaf surface loss caused by the cereal leaf beetle. *Landsc. Ecol.* 35 (10), 2225–2238. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10980-020-01097-3>.
- Le Clech, S., Van Bussel, L.G.J., Lof, M.E., De Knegt, B., Szentirmai, I., Andersen, E., 2024. Effects of linear landscape elements on multiple ecosystem services in contrasting agricultural landscapes. *Ecosyst. Serv.* 67, 101616. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecoser.2024.101616>.
- Leonhardt, H., Hüttel, S., Lakes, T., Wesemeyer, M., Wolff, S., 2023. Use Cases of the Integrated Administration and Control System's Plot-Level Data: Protocol and Pilot Analysis for a Systematic Mapping Review. *Ger. J. Agric. Econ.* 72 (3–4). <https://doi.org/10.30430/gjae.2023.0385>.
- LGB., 2022a. Agrarantragsdaten. (<https://geobroker.geobasis-bb.de/gbss.php?MODE=GetProductInformation&PRODUCTID=996f8fd1-c662-4975-b680-3b611fcb5d1f>).
- LGB., 2022b. Biotopkataster in Brandenburg—INSPIRE Download Service (WFS-LFU-BBK). (<https://geoportal.brandenburg.de/detailansichtdienst/render?url=https://geoportal.brandenburg.de/gs-json/xml?fileid=95DC1532-DEDA-4B8A-B1E8-B3DCB50EB4E7>).
- LGB., 2022c. Biodiversionsgefährdung. (<https://geoportal.brandenburg.de/detailansichtdienst/render?url=https://geoportal.brandenburg.de/gs-json/xml?fileid=776fa91c-2fc9-4a58-8daf-589627397bd1>).

- LGB., 2022d. Landwirtschaftliches Ertragspotenzial. (<https://geoportal.brandenburg.de/detailsichtdienst/render?url=https://geoportal.brandenburg.de/gs-json/xml?fileid=bfaf655-9fa0-4b42-9c9b-43d00342e7ca>).
- 2020 LGB., 2020. Förderkulisse für die Blühstreifen-Richtlinie. (<https://geobroker.geobasis-bb.de/gbss.php?MODE=GetProductInformation&PRODUCTID=d1e4be15-25c8-4587-8486-e138527366c4>).
- Maechler, M., Rousseeuw, P., Struyf, A., Hubert, M., & Hornik, K., 2023. cluster: Cluster Analysis Basics and Extensions (R package version 2.1.6) [Computer software]. CRAN. <https://CRAN.R-project.org/package=cluste>.
- Maes, J., Teller, A., Erhard, M., Condé, S., Vallecillo, S., Barredo, J.I., Santos-Martín, F., 2020. Mapping and assessment of ecosystems and their services: An EU wide ecosystem assessment in support of the EU biodiversity strategy. Publications Office.
- Marja, R., Kleijn, D., Tschamtké, T., Klein, A.M., Frank, T., Batáry, P., 2019. Effectiveness of agri-environmental management on pollinators is moderated more by ecological contrast than by landscape structure or land-use intensity. *Ecol. Lett.* 22 (9), 1493–1500. <https://doi.org/10.1111/ele.13339>.
- Marja, R., Tschamtké, T., Batáry, P., 2022. Increasing landscape complexity enhances species richness of farmland arthropods, agri-environment schemes also abundance – A meta-analysis. *Agric., Ecosyst. Environ.* 326. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.agee.2021.107822>.
- Martin, E.A., Dainese, M., Clough, Y., Báldi, A., Bommarco, R., Gagic, V., Garratt, M.P.D., Holzschuh, A., Kleijn, D., Kovács-Hostyánszki, A., Marini, L., Potts, S.G., Smith, H.G., Al Hassan, D., Albrecht, M., Andersson, G.K.S., Asís, J.D., Aviron, S., Balzan, M.V., Steffan-Dewenter, I., 2019. The interplay of landscape composition and configuration: new pathways to manage functional biodiversity and agroecosystem services across Europe. *Ecol. Lett.* 22 (7), 1083–1094. <https://doi.org/10.1111/ele.13265>.
- Massfeller, A., Meraner, M., Hüttel, S., Uehleke, R., 2022. Data on farmers' acceptance of results-based agri-environmental schemes. *Data Brief.* 45, 108642. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.dib.2022.108642>.
- Meyer, B.C., Wolf, T., Grabau, R., 2012. A multifunctional assessment method for compromise optimisation of linear landscape elements. *Ecol. Indic.* 22, 53–63. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecolind.2011.07.020>.
- Muchane, M.N., Sileshi, G.W., Gripenberg, S., Jonsson, M., Pumarino, L., Barrios, E., 2020. Agroforestry boosts soil health in the humid and sub-humid tropics: a meta-analysis. *Agric., Ecosyst. Environ.* 295, 106899. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.agee.2020.106899>.
- Pe'er, G., Finn, J.A., Díaz, M., Birkenstock, M., Lakner, S., Röder, N., Kazakova, Y., Šumrada, T., Bezák, P., Concepción, E.D., Dänhardt, J., Morales, M.B., Rac, I., Špulerová, J., Schindler, S., Stavrínides, M., Targetti, S., Viaggi, D., Vogiatzakis, I.N., Guymard, H., 2022. How can the European Common Agricultural Policy help halt biodiversity loss? Recommendations by over 300 experts. *Conserv. Lett.* 15 (6). <https://doi.org/10.1111/conl.12901>.
- Plant, R.E., n.d. Spatial data analysis in ecology and agriculture using R. Retrieved April 30, 2023, from <https://www.routledge.com/Spatial-Data-Analysis-in-Ecology-and-Agriculture-Using-R/Plant/p/book/9780367732325>.
- Polasky, S., Nelson, E., Lonsdorf, E., Fackler, P., Starfield, A., 2005. Conserving species in a working landscape: land use with biological and economic objectives. *Ecol. Appl.* 15 (4), 1387–1401. <https://doi.org/10.1890/03-5423>.
- Ramankutty, N., Mehrabi, Z., Waha, K., Jarvis, L., Kremen, C., Herrero, M., & Rieseberg, L.H., 2018. Trends in Global Agricultural Land Use: Implications for Environmental Health and Food Security. (<https://doi.org/10.1146/annurev-arplant-042817-040256>), 69, 789–815. (<https://doi.org/10.1146/annurev-arplant-042817-040256>).
- Ridding, L.E., Redhead, J.W., Oliver, T.H., Schmucki, R., McGinlay, J., Graves, A.R., Morris, J., Bradbury, R.B., King, H., Bullock, J.M., 2018. The importance of landscape characteristics for the delivery of cultural ecosystem services. *J. Environ. Manag.* 206, 1145–1154. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jenvman.2017.11.066>.
- Rieb, J.T., Bennett, E.M., 2020. Landscape structure as a mediator of ecosystem service interactions. *Landscape Ecol.* 35 (12), 2863–2880. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10980-020-01117-2>.
- Rubio-Delgado, J., Schnabel, S., Lavado-Contador, J.F., Schmutz, U., 2024. Small woody features in agricultural areas: agroforestry systems of overlooked significance in Europe. *Agric. Syst.* 218. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.agsy.2024.103973>.
- Schaan, L. N., 2025a. Landscape features spatial dataset for Brandenburg, Germany (1.0) [Data set]. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15182495>.
- Schaan, L. N., 2025b. Computational notebook to process the landscape features spatial dataset for Brandenburg, Germany (1.0). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15180670>.
- Schroeder, L.A., Chaplin, S., & Isselstein, J., 2015. What influences farmers' acceptance of agri-environment schemes? An ex-post application of the "Theory of Planned Behaviour" - a quantitative assessment - Landbauforschung - Applied Agricultural and Forestry Research, 1/2015, 15–28. (<https://doi.org/10.3220/LBF1440149868000>).
- TEEB, DE., 2018. The Value of Nature for Economy and Society. A Synthesis of Natural Capital Germany – TEEB. Helmholtz Centre for Environmental Research – UFZ.
- Trujillo-Barrera, A., Pennings, J.M.E., Hofen, D., 2016. Understanding producers' motives for adopting sustainable practices: the role of expected rewards, risk perception and risk tolerance. *Eur. Rev. Agric. Econ.* 43 (3), 359–382. <https://doi.org/10.1093/erae/jbv038>.
- Tschamtké, T., Grass, I., Wanger, T.C., Westphal, C., Batáry, P., 2021. Beyond organic farming – harnessing biodiversity-friendly landscapes. *Trends Ecol. Evol.* 1–12. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tree.2021.06.010>.
- Tschamtké, T., Klein, A.M., Krueß, A., Steffan-Dewenter, I., Thies, C., 2005. Landscape perspectives on agricultural intensification and biodiversity—ecosystem service management. *Ecol. Lett.* 8 (8), 857–874. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1461-0248.2005.00782.x>.
- Tschamtké, T., Tylianakis, J.M., Rand, T.A., Didham, R.K., Fahrig, L., Batáry, P., Bengtsson, J., Clough, Y., Crist, T.O., Dormann, C.F., Ewers, R.M., Fründ, J., Holt, R. D., Holzschuh, A., Klein, A.M., Kleijn, D., Kremen, C., Landis, D.A., Laurance, W., Westphal, C., 2012. Landscape moderation of biodiversity patterns and processes—eight hypotheses. *Biol. Rev.* 87 (3), 661–685. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1469-185X.2011.00216.x>.
- Uthes, S., Kiesel, J., 2020. Creating a synthetic landscape: spatial allocation of non-spatial single farm data. *Agric. Syst.* 177, 102740. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.agsy.2019.102740>.
- van der Zanden, E.H., Levers, C., Verburg, P.H., Kuemmerle, T., 2016. Representing composition, spatial structure and management intensity of European agricultural landscapes: a new typology. *Landscape Urban Plan.* 150, 36–49. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.landurbplan.2016.02.005>.
- van Klink, R., Bowler, D.E., Gongalsky, K.B., Swengel, A.B., Gentile, A., Chase, J.M., 2020. Meta-analysis reveals declines in terrestrial but increases in freshwater insect abundances. *Science* 368 (6489), 417–420. https://doi.org/10.1126/SCIENCE.AAX9931/SUPPL_FILE/AAX9931-VANKLINK-SM.PDF.
- van Klink, R., Bowler, D.E., Gongalsky, K.B., Shen, M., Swengel, S.R., Chase, J.M., 2024. Disproportionate declines of formerly abundant species underlie insect loss. *Nature* 628 (8007), 359–364. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41586-023-06861-4>.
- Venghaus, S., Acosta, L., 2018. To produce or not to produce: an analysis of bioenergy and crop production decisions based on farmer typologies in Brandenburg, Germany. *Reg. Environ. Change* 18 (2), 521–532. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10113-017-1226-1>.
- Vermunt, D.A., Verweij, P.A., Verburg, R.W., 2020. What Hampers Implementation of Integrated Landscape Approaches in Rural Landscapes? *Curr. Landscape Ecol. Rep.* 5 (4), 99–115. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s40823-020-00057-6>.
- Weissteiner, C.J., García-Feced, C., Paracchini, M.L., 2016. A new view on EU agricultural landscapes: quantifying patchiness to assess farmland heterogeneity. *Ecol. Indic.* 61, 317–327. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecolind.2015.09.032>.
- Wezel, A., Bellon, S., Doré, T., Francis, C., Vallod, D., David, C., 2009. Agroecology as a science, a movement and a practice. *A review. Agron. Sustain. Dev.* 29. <https://doi.org/10.1051/agro/2009004>.
- Wilcox, B.P., Basant, S., Olariu, H., Leite, P.A.M., 2022. Ecohydrological connectivity: a unifying framework for understanding how woody plant encroachment alters the water cycle in drylands. *Front. Environ. Sci.* 10. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fenvs.2022.934535>.
- Wojtynia, N., Van Dijk, J., Derks, M., Groot Koerkamp, P.W.G., Hekkert, M.P., 2023. Spheres of transformation: exploring personal, political and practical drivers of farmer agency and behaviour change in the Netherlands. *Environ. Innov. Soc. Transit.* 49, 100776. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.eist.2023.100776>.
- Wolff, S., Hüttel, S., Nendel, C., Lakes, T., 2021. Agricultural landscapes in Brandenburg, Germany: an analysis of characteristics and spatial patterns. *Int. J. Environ. Res.* 15 (3), 487–507. <https://doi.org/10.1007/S41742-021-00328-Y/TABLES/4>.